
ANXIETY AND ENTHUSIASM OF TEACHERS TOWARDS ICT USAGE IN SECONDARY SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN AWKA SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined anxiety and enthusiasm of teachers towards ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. The study was guided by two research questions. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 604 teachers (60 males and 544 females) from the 19 public secondary schools in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. All the 604 teachers were used for the study due to relatively manageable size of the population. A researcher-developed instrument titled “Anxiety and Enthusiasm of Teachers to Information and Communication Technology Usage in School Management Questionnaire (AETICTUSMQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts from Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. The internal consistency of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha which yielded reliability value of 0.79. The instruments were administered by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Anambra State. A total of 604 copies of the questionnaires were distributed and 593 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 98% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed that teachers show high enthusiasm to ICT usage in secondary school management based on gender in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. It was also found that teachers have low anxiety to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Post Primary Schools Service Commission should organize annual capacity building programmes in form of workshop and seminars for teachers to update their skills, knowledge and continue to reduce their anxiety to the use of ICT in school management.

Keywords: Anxiety, Enthusiasm, Teachers, Information, Communication, Technology, School Management

Introduction

Secondary education is the post basic learning opportunities offer to students to equip skills and knowledge that prepare them for different career and to make positive contributions to the progress of the society. Onyia and Abetang (2024) opined that secondary education serves as a 'producer' (input for tertiary level of education) and a 'consumer' (absorbs the output from primary level of education). Secondary education empowers children to know their basic rights and responsibilities in the society. Akhibi and Omenyi (2024) opined out that secondary education equally provides opportunities for pupils to acquire additional knowledge, skills and traits beyond what is offered at primary school level. The quality of secondary education is highly depended on the quality of teachers.

Teacher is a trained and certified person who impart knowledge, skills and shape the character of learners in the classroom. Osiesi, Odinko and Oke (2022) defined teacher as a professional who convey unto learners the life needed skills, knowledge and experience for a functional living. Teacher is responsible for planning instructional activities and implementing curriculum of secondary education at classroom level. Aladetan (2023) defined teacher as the implementer of the curriculum to impart the requisite knowledge, skill and attitude in the pupils. The author added that it is the responsibilities of teachers include preparation for classes by writing suitable lesson notes with supportive instructional materials, delivering effectively in the classroom, managing students in the classroom, marking pupils' assignments, keeping pupils' records, participating and helping pupils participate in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities. These responsibilities of teachers show that they have some key roles to play in school management.

School management is the tasks of planning, mobilizing and coordinating the use of the available resources for the accomplishment of education institutional goals and objectives. Saleh and Apollos (2024) defined school management as the act and practice of the organization, coordination and administration of educational establishments like secondary school education. School management is the act of communication, delegating tasks, maintaining discipline, good interpersonal relationships, building reputable school image to achieve set educational goals. School management is described by Onyia and Abetang (2024), as the utilization and systematic coordination of available resources (human, material, finances, time and information) towards the achievement of stated educational objectives. School management is the process of organizing and overseeing daily activities to ensure smooth operation of educational institutions. There are consistent changes in the ways of managing affairs over the years. One of the ways to cope with the changes is the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) into school management.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is electronic devices and software for gathering, classifying, storing, retrieving, sharing and utilizing information to perform a given task. It is computerized systems for processing and managing data in an organization. According to Nkemjika and Raji (2020), ICT is a wide range of computerized technologies that enables communication and the electronic capturing, processing, and transmission of information. ICT facilities include desktop laptops, printers, photocopying machines, projectors, mobile devices, scanners and internet connectivity among others. Adameji (2024) noted that ICT facilities also includes projectors, radio, television, telephone and other equipment with their accessories and applications that help to pass messages from a message sender to the intended receiver without undue distortion. ICT is defined by Abbas and Abubakar (2024), as the integration of computing, networking, and information processing technologies and their applications in sharing information from a source to its destination.

The authors added that ICT is a combination of computer applications and communication technology for gathering, processing, storing, and disseminating Information. The integration of ICT in managing activities in the classroom could be influenced by the attitude of teachers.

Attitude of teachers is the way members of teaching perceive, think and integrate ICT facilities in managing activities in the classroom. It is a teacher characteristic and component of teacher personality, and it can impact their interactions with students and the overall classroom environment (Ramadass & Shah, 2022). Attitude of teachers towards the use of ICT may be positive or negative. Positive attitudes could make teachers to integrate ICT in school management, while negative attitude could discourage them from utilizing technological devices in school management. There are some dimensions of teachers' attitudes toward ICT usage in school management. The dimensions to evaluate the teachers' attitude towards the usage of ICT in school system are self-efficacy, anxiety, avoidance, confidence, enthusiasm and liking (Bariu & Chun, 2022). Similarly, Semerci and Aydin (2018) noted that teachers' attitude toward ICT use in education could be determined using ICT willingness and ICT anxiety. This study focused on anxiety and enthusiasm.

ICT anxiety is feeling of discomfort and nervousness in using electronic devices in executing tasks. ICT Anxiety is defined by Osisanwo, Ehioghae and Abdulsalaam (2019), as intense dread, apprehension, or worry towards the use of innovative devices in carrying out assigned roles. It is negative emotional responses and uneasiness in the use of ICT in managing affairs in the classroom. Lalitha and Sharath (2023) noted that ICT anxiety is the mixture of fear, apprehension and hope felt when planning to interact and use digital devices. Anxiety of teachers could make them to be afraid to use ICT in school management. ICT anxiety could make teachers feel uncomfortable and frightened to digital devices in managing classroom affairs. Shoiria (2021) noted that when teachers suffer from ICT anxiety, they have a fear about thinking or working with digital devices in performing their duties in schools. Anxiety could lead to a negative attitude towards the use of ICT in carrying out official duties in school. Teachers with ICT anxiety may feel frustration and worried which could lead to avoidance of using electronic devices in performing their duties.

Enthusiasm is the eagerness and strong interest to use a particular tool or actively engage in an activity. Enthusiasm is described by Xiao-qui, Ying-yin, Ke and Guan-yu (2023), as positive emotion states like happiness and excitement of teachers towards participating in an activity. Enthusiasm is considered a crucial aspect of teachers' attitude which compels or motivates them to use ICT in school management. Joseph, Okeagu, Guma, Attah and Enoch (2023) pointed out that when teachers are enthusiastic, they are more likely to use ICT to effectively communicate their passion to their students and inspire them to learn. ICT enthusiasm could make teachers to exhibit healthy and positive attitude towards integrating ICT in running affairs of the classroom. Elias, Musengamana and Mebrahtu (2023) asserted that enthusiasm of teachers towards usage of ICT make them to feel excited and interested to apply technological facilities in controlling affairs of classroom. Enthusiastic about usage of ICT in school and classroom management could create a conducive work environment for teachers irrespective of their gender.

Some teachers tend to resort to manual ways of managing affairs in classroom probably due to negative attitude to use of ICT in public secondary schools in Awka South LGA, Anambra State. Okeke and Ikediugwu (2021) maintained that it is worrisome that records keeping remain manually-based and unorganized which make it difficult to keep track of managerial and classroom activities such as school attendance, monitoring of examinations and planning of instructional programmes in public secondary schools in

Anambra State. Abosede, Idris and Wilfred-Bonse (2023) noted that teachers still exhibit considerable technology phobia in secondary schools in Nigeria. The phobia among some teachers in the use of ICT in managing affairs tend to create classroom problems in public secondary schools in Awka LGA, Anambra State. These classroom problems range from irregular marking of classroom attendance register, indiscipline and delaying in computing students' results among others. These problems prompted the investigation into the anxiety and enthusiasm of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine anxiety and enthusiasm of teachers towards ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. ascertain the anxiety of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.
2. examine enthusiasm of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the anxiety of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?
2. What is the enthusiasm of male and female teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?

Methods

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised 604 teachers (60 males and 544 females) from the 19 public secondary schools in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. There was no sampling since the entire population is relatively small and manageable. Therefore, the researcher applied census sampling technique in selecting all 604 public secondary school teachers in Awka South LGA for the study. According to Singh and Masuku (2014), census technique is appropriate approach for a study which intends to use the entire population because is relatively size as the sample for a research work. Thus, the 604 teachers are relatively size and manageable by the researcher.

A researcher-developed instrument titled "Anxiety and Enthusiasm of Teachers towards Information and Communication Technology Usage in School Management Questionnaire (AETICTUSMQ)" was used for data collection. The instrument was structured by the researcher based on literature review and suggestions of experts. The instrument had two sections- A and B. Section A contains three items on respondents' background information covering respondents' gender. Section B had four clusters A and B which contained 20 items on anxiety and enthusiasm of teachers towards ICT usage. Cluster A had 10 items on anxiety of teachers to ICT usage in school management had 10 items and Cluster B which focused on enthusiasm of teachers to ICT usage in school management had 10 items. The instrument was structured on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The face validation of the instrument was determined by three experts in the Department of Educational Foundations, all in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. The experts made several suggestions that

include starting of the items with small letters and separation of double-barrel items. Their suggestions were used to produce the final version of the instruments used for data collection. Cronbach alpha method which involved single administration of 30 copies of the instrument to 30 teachers in public secondary schools in Awka North LGA, which was outside the area of study but share similar characteristics in terms of school management. The data obtained were subjected to test for internal consistency using Cronbach alpha. The co-efficient obtained for clusters A and B of AETICTUSMRS were 0.77 and 0.78 respectively and overall coefficient was 0.78. Thus, the researcher considered the instrument to be reliable for the study.

Data was collected by the researcher with the help of three research assistants who are teachers in secondary schools. The research assistants were briefed by the researcher on the content and mode of the instruments administration. A total of 604 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 593 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 98% return rate. At the end of the exercise, copies of the questionnaire properly filled and successfully retrieved were used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The decision criteria on the research questions are that any item with a mean score equal or above 2.50 indicated agreement, while the item with a mean score below 2.50 indicated disagreement.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the anxiety of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on the Anxiety of Teachers to ICT Usage in Secondary School Management

S/N	ITEMS	Male Teachers (n=57)			Female Teachers (n=536)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Feel apprehensive about using computer to manage students' records	2.36	1.07	Disagree	2.41	1.06	Disagree
2	Hesitate to use electronic devices to manage lesson plan for the fear of making mistakes that cannot be easily corrected	2.41	1.09	Disagree	2.35	0.95	Disagree
3	Feel scared of using computer to organize my lesson notes to avoid loss of some of my reasoning skills	2.48	1.01	Disagree	2.40	1.02	Disagree
4	Find electronic devices unnecessary in managing school affairs	2.33	1.04	Disagree	2.37	1.06	Disagree
5	Like to avoid the use of digital devices because they are unfamiliar to use	2.44	1.05	Disagree	2.38	1.08	Disagree
6	Find it intimidating to use electronic devices to manage school affairs	2.47	0.97	Disagree	2.45	1.04	Disagree
7	Feel insecure about my ability to use digital devices to manage students' attendance	2.46	1.01	Disagree	2.39	0.98	Disagree
8	Find it difficult in understanding the technical aspects of using computer to manage classroom activities	2.54	1.01	Agree	2.51	0.96	Agree
9	Panic when presented with computer to manage the activities of students	2.48	1.07	Disagree	2.38	1.02	Disagree
10	Feel visible signs of nervousness such as sweaty palms in using computer in managing school affairs	2.53	1.00	Agree	2.56	1.11	Agree
Cluster Mean		2.45	1.03	Disagree	2.43	1.02	Disagree

Result presented in Table 2 revealed that the mean scores of male and female teachers for items 1-7 and 9 are below 2.50 indicating disagreement with the items as their anxiety to ICT usage in secondary school management. The mean scores of male and female teachers for items 8 and 10 are above 2.50 indicating agreement with the items as their anxiety to ICT usage in secondary school management.

The cluster standard scores which stood at 1.03 and 1.02 for male and female teachers respectively indicated homogeneity amongst their responses in each item. The clusters mean of 2.45 and 2.43 obtained by male and female teachers which are below the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicated teachers have low anxiety to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the enthusiasm of teachers to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on the Enthusiasm of Teachers to ICT Usage in Secondary School Management

S/ N	ITEMS	Male Teachers (n=57)			Female Teachers (n=536)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
11	Enjoy to use Microsoft Excel to process the results of students	2.84	1.06	Agree	2.75	1.09	Agree
12	Feel comfortable using computer spread sheet to prepare students class schedules	2.56	1.10	Agree	2.59	1.05	Agree
13	Find it interesting to use computer in keeping records of classroom facilities	2.89	1.06	Agree	2.77	1.11	Agree
14	Like to use e-mail to communicate regularly with parents to seek their assistance in helping their children to learn	2.76	1.01	Agree	2.88	1.04	Agree
15	Enjoy to preserve school meeting proceedings in Google cloud	2.61	1.13	Agree	2.60	1.00	Agree
16	Feel excited to participate in organizing orientation programme for students utilizing projector	2.57	1.09	Agree	2.71	1.07	Agree
17	Like to plan the co-curricular activities of students using computer	2.69	1.00	Agree	2.63	1.12	Agree
18	Like to manage instructional time using digital devices	2.51	0.97	Agree	2.63	1.11	Agree
19	Enjoy to use visual/audio to manage classroom instructional activities	2.65	0.99	Agree	2.58	1.04	Agree
10	Like to collaborate with my principal in prepare school budget with Microsoft Excel	2.60	1.08	Agree	2.55	1.03	Agree
Cluster Mean		2.67	1.05	Agree	2.68	1.07	Agree

Data analysis as shown in Table 2 revealed that the mean scores of male and female teachers for all items are above 2.50 indicating agreement with the items as their enthusiasm to ICT usage in secondary school management. The cluster standard scores which stood at 1.04 and 1.05 for male and female teachers respectively indicated similarity in their responses amongst each cluster. The clusters mean of 2.58 and 2.65 obtained by male and female teachers which are above the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicated teachers show high enthusiasm to ICT usage in secondary school management based on gender in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

Discussion of the Findings

The result of the study revealed that teachers have low anxiety to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Lalitha and Sharath (2023) showed that there was a low ICT anxiety between male and female teacher trainees. The dissimilarity in the area of the studies could explain the disagreement with the finding. Low anxiety to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State showed that they do not Feel apprehensive, insecure, visible signs of nervousness or hesitate to use in ICT in managing affairs in the classroom. Male and female teachers have low anxiety to ICT usage in school management probably due to they are conversant with the benefits of utilizing some ICT devices and social media in carrying out their job. Low ICT anxiety of teachers showed that they exhibit positive attitude to the use of computer, internet and digital facilities in carrying out activities. Male and female teachers feel less worried and nervous about ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State.

It was revealed that teachers exhibited high enthusiasm to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. This contradicted the finding of Joseph, Okeagu, Guma, Attah and Enoch (2023) which showed that teachers have low enthusiasm towards ICT usage in secondary schools. The difference in geographical location could be responsible for the disagreement with the findings. This finding indicated that teachers feel interested, intense excited and motivated in using ICT to manage activities in the classroom. The teachers exhibited high enthusiasm to ICT usage in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State through feeling comfortable to use ICT to process the results of students, prepare class schedules, keep records of classroom facilities, communicate regularly with parents and manage instructional time. Male and female teachers are optimistic about the use of ICT in school management.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that male and female teachers have high enthusiasm towards the use of ICT in secondary school management in Awka South LGA of Anambra State. They showed low anxiety to the use of ICT in secondary school management.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Post Primary Schools Service Commission should organize annual capacity building programmes in form of workshop and seminars for teachers to up-date their skills, knowledge and continue to reduce their anxiety to the use of ICT in school management.
2. Principals should organize regular interactive sessions for teachers to improve their enthusiasm to the use of ICT in school management.

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